

AGRICULTURAL SKILLS DEVELOPED AMONG THE GRADE 5 LEARNERS IN THE COURSE OF IMPLEMENTATION OF GULAYAN SA PAARALAN IN PLARIDEL DISTRICT, SCHOOLS DIVISION OF QUEZON

Thelma Q. Escobar, Dr. Alexander M. Pascua

Marinduque State College Boac, Marinduque Extension of Graduate Programs to Quezonian Educational College, Inc. Atimonan, Quezon Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11143273>

ABSTRACT

This research focuses on assessing the impact of the Gulayan sa Paaralan Project (GPP) on the development of agricultural skills among the grade 5 learners in the Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon, Philippines. Plaridel District is situated along the coastal area of Lamon Bay, bordered by the town of Atimonan to the west, Gumaca to the east, Unisan to the south and Lamon Bay to the north. Within the town of Plaridel there are four elementary Schools: Concepcion Elementary School, Ilosong Elementary School, Plaridel Central School, and Tanauan Elementary School. The study employed an evidence-centered design (ECD) approach. This approach focuses on gathering evidence to assess learners' agricultural skills and provides direction for designing innovative task types, involving 156 grade 5 learners from four schools. The selection of 5th-grade learners in the Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon is appropriate because these learners have been actively involved in the implementation of the Gulayan sa Paaralan Program. Findings indicate that learners have least agricultural skills, with males demonstrating higher proficiency than females. Among the schools, Tanauan showed the highest perceived agricultural skills. The study concludes that the GPP is effective in promoting food security and enhancing agricultural skills, but improvements are needed, particularly in tool identification and pest control. It suggests further investigation into gender differences and highlights the importance of effective program implementation. The recommendations include implementing creative and engaging techniques, organizing gardening competitions, and providing guidance to students throughout the activities. These recommendations aim to enhance the effectiveness of the GPP and improve students' agricultural skills.

Keywords: *Agricultural knowledges, Agricultural Skills, Assessment, Gulayan sa Paaralan Program*

INTRODUCTION

Food scarcity is a complex issue that affects local and global economies. The growing population necessitates an increased food supply to meet its needs, but there are instances where the supply falls short, leading to food shortages. Several factors contribute to this problem. Natural disasters like volcanic eruptions and other disturbances can disrupt the supply chains required for the transportation of raw resources and food. Additionally, macroeconomic crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic hinder the work of farmers and the transportation of agricultural goods, as operations are forced to suspend due to lockdown measures. Moreover, globalization has played a significant role in exacerbating food shortages, as disruptions in the production operations of major food-producing countries can have a ripple effect on the global food supply market (Sayadi et al., 2019).

If no measures are taken to address food scarcity and insecurity, the community will face numerous negative repercussions. According to Conserve Energy Future (n.d.), there is a significant correlation between food instability and hunger, which can lead to poverty and the prevalence of acute and chronic diseases requiring hospitalization. This creates a domino effect, as increased food insecurity contributes to higher poverty rates, mortality rates, and disease incidence, particularly among children.

Despite the Philippines' transition into an industrialized economy, it remains classified as an agricultural country, with a large portion of the population relying on agriculture for their livelihoods (Piñol, 2020). The country possesses fertile land that has the potential to produce enough food to sustain its population if effectively managed. The main crops grown in the Philippines include rice, coconut, corn, coffee, pineapple, tobacco, and abaca, while secondary crops include camote, cassava, peanut, calamansi, rubber, and cotton. However, the agricultural sector has been adversely affected by various factors such as environmental damage caused by climate change and the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic. In fact, Piñol (2020) highlights that Filipino food insecurity has been exacerbated by the reduced production of food due to the COVID-19 lockdown.

One effective approach to addressing this issue is through indoor or organic gardening. Despite criticisms regarding low yields, organic farming has gained popularity due to consumer demand concerning the impact of opportunity in organic farming for sustainable agricultural development Mariappan et al. (2019) Agriculture is the main source of income for humans. yields In a study on soil fertility and biodiversity in organic farming, Maeder et al. (2022) found that crop were 20% lower in organic systems. However, these systems showed a reduction in fertilizer and energy inputs by 34% to

53% and a decrease in pesticide usage by 97%. The enhanced soil fertility and higher biodiversity associated with organic farming may lead to decreased reliance on external inputs. One major challenge in both organic and conventional farming systems is the management of weeds, as surveys of commercial farmers and assessments by researchers consistently identify weeds as a top constraint to efficient production. Herbicide-resistant weeds have been observed since the early years of synthetic herbicide development in the 1950s and 1960s. A two-year field experiment was conducted to assess the effect of different dates of sowing and chemical weeds control on the weed indices in berseem during the rabi seasons of 2020. (Yadav et al., 2023)

While many gardeners assume that any organic product is automatically safe, it is important to note that this is not always the case. Products and practices need to be evaluated on a case-by-case basis to determine their safety and effectiveness for their intended purpose. Furthermore, Mourão et al. (2019) found a positive correlation between the frequency of visits to organic gardens and a higher perception of subjective happiness. This suggests that individuals who visit gardens more frequently tend to experience greater happiness compared to those who visit less often. The highest accuracy in predicting the likelihood that a consumer will have an intention to buy organic products. (Taghikhah et al., 2021)

Given that children are the age group most affected by food insecurity and shortages due to their high nutritional needs, it is crucial to involve them in activities that promote food security. Conserve Energy Future (n.d.) emphasizes the importance of food security for children in increasing their engagement in school activities and social connections with peers. To address these concerns, the Department of Education (DepEd), in collaboration with the Department of Agriculture (DAR), has launched an organic and planting program called the Gulayan sa Paaralan Program (GPP). This program aims to enhance agricultural output in the community while equipping children with valuable skills and knowledge.

The GPP primarily focuses on school gardening as a contribution to the feeding program, promoting awareness of locally grown crops and vegetables. The Department of Agriculture remains dedicated to supporting and sustaining the Gulayan sa Paaralan Program by providing seeds, garden tools, and equipment. As stated in the DepEd memo dated December 14, 2016, the implementation of the GPP in public elementary and secondary schools nationwide, through the Bureau of Learner Support Service, Schools Health Division (BLSS-SHP), aims to promote food security in schools and communities. The program encourages self-help food production activities, instills values among learners, and fosters an appreciation for agriculture as a life support system. Specific objectives include promoting vegetable production in public schools, establishing, and maintaining school gardens as a ready source of vegetables for sustenance, serving as a learning laboratory, producing school-grown vegetables to enhance nutrition, showcasing small-scale food production models, and instilling values of gardening, good health, nutrition, and care for others among learners.

Given these circumstances, the author intends to conduct this study to assess the agricultural skills developed among students during the implementation of the GPP in Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon. Additionally, the study will serve as feedback on the performance of the GPP in Plaridel District, providing insights necessary for formulating effective interventions based on the study's findings.

Research Questions

The research aims to determine the agricultural skills developed among the grade five learners during implementation of Gulayan sa Paaralan in Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon.

Specifically, it will answer the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following?
 - 1.1 sex
 - 1.2 area/school

2. What agricultural skills in the following activities are developed among the learners due to Gulayan sa Paaralan?
 - 2.1 Essential Skills
 - 2.1.1 Clearing and land preparation.
 - 2.1.2 Selection of planting materials and methods of planting.
 - 2.1.3 Systematic planting strategy.
 - 2.1.4 Maintenance and caring for plants.
 - 2.1.5 Identification of garden tools and other materials
 - 2.1.6 Proper care of garden tools.
 - 2.2 Special Skills
 - 2.2.1 Identification and control of destructive insects.
 - 2.2.2 Organic fertilizer making.
 - 2.2.3 Harvesting and Marketing

3. Is there a significant difference in the agricultural skills of learners when grouped into the following profile?
 - 3.1 Sex
 - 3.2 area/school

4. What intervention program could be proposed by the researcher based on the study's findings?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The research locale for this study is the District of Plaridel, Schools Division of Quezon. Plaridel is a small town located in the province of Quezon, Philippines. It is situated along the coastal area of Lamon Bay, bordered by the town of Atimonan to the west, Gumaca to the east, Unisan to the south, and Lamon Bay to the north.

Plaridel is classified as a fifth-class municipality, and according to the 2020 census, it has a population of approximately 10,129 people. The town was established in 1962 through Republic Act No. 3493, which designated specific territories from the Municipality of Atimonan to form Plaridel. The total land area of Plaridel is approximately 18.19 square kilometers, with a population density of 557 inhabitants per square kilometer.

Within the town of Plaridel, there are four elementary schools: Plaridel Central School, Ilosong Elementary School, Concepcion Elementary School, and Tanauan Elementary School, which is in Barangay Paaralan, Barangay Ilosong, Barangay Concepcion, and Barangay Tanauan, respectively. Additionally, there are two secondary schools in Plaridel, namely Plaridel Memorial School and Concepcion National High School.

The researcher selected Plaridel as the study area because it has a significant amount of land suitable for farming purposes, making it an appropriate setting for investigating agricultural skills among students.

Figure No. 2. Location Map of Plaridel

Population and Sample

The population for this study consists of 5th-grade learners from the Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon. The researcher chose this population as representative of the entire population of learners in the district. According to Holmes et al. (2020), 5th-grade learners have been found to possess the highest level of agricultural literacy based on their study titled "Exploring Elementary Learners' Agricultural and Scientific Knowledge Using Evidence Centered Design Among K to 12 Learners." The research evaluates the impact participation in school garden programs on fifth grade students garden knowledge.

The selection of 5th-grade learners in the Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon is also appropriate because these learners have been actively involved in the implementation of the Gulayan sa Paaralan Program (GPP) by the Department of Education (DepEd). The GPP is a government program promoting school gardening and agricultural activities. By focusing on this specific population, the study aims to assess the agrarian skills and agricultural literacy that students have developed through their participation in the GPP.

Table 1

The Population of Grade 5 Learners in Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon.

School	Number of Grade 5 Learners
Concepcion Elementary School	17
Ilosong Elementary School	37
Plaridel Central School	78
Tanauan Elementary School	24
Grand Total	156

Table 1 presents the population of Grade 5 learners in the Plaridel District, Schools

Table 1 presents the population of Grade 5 learners in the Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon. As depicted in the table, there are a total of 156 learners, who served as samples for the study. To be qualified as respondents, the learners needed to be in the fifth grade and have participated in GPP activities prior to the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic. Their responses were crucial in acquiring the necessary evidence to support the researcher's claims and were used in formulating interventions to enhance the program. The biggest population of respondents were coming from Plaridel Central School with the total of 78 learners and this is attributed to the multiple barangays covered by the school unlike Ilosong where only two barangays were covered (37 learners), Concepcion with one barangay (17 learners) and Tanauan with one barangay as well (24 learners).

According to M. Tira (2020) the growing number of people is living in cities and town and this explain the highest population of learners displayed by Plaridel Central school, followed by second larger area the Ilosong Elementary School then Tanauan Elementary School and lastly Concepcion Elementary school.

Research Instrument

To collect the necessary data for this study, a questionnaire was chosen as the research instrument. The questionnaire consisted of two parts.

The first part focused on gathering the demographic profile of the respondents, including their name, sex, and area/school. This information is crucial for drawing implications, especially in determining any significant differences between demographic factors and the agricultural skills of the respondents.

The second part of the questionnaire comprised a series of statements related to different activities conducted in the GPP. These statements were assessed using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from Highly Skill to No Skill, to measure the skills of the learners. The questionnaire was further divided into two categories: essential skills and special skills. The questions were designed specifically to address the objectives of the study.

The use of a questionnaire as the research instrument allowed the researcher to gather measurable data using the Likert scale, facilitating the drawing of conclusions for the study.

Content Validity of the Research Instrument

The content validity of the research instrument, which is the questionnaire, was ensured by presenting it to the adviser for comments, suggestions, and further improvements. The purpose of this step was to validate that the questionnaire contains accurate and relevant questions aligned with the objectives of the study.

The designated validator, who is the adviser, carefully evaluated the questionnaire to assess its appropriateness, clarity, and relevance to the research topic. Any necessary revisions or modifications were made based on the recommendations and feedback provided by the validator.

By undergoing this validation process, the questionnaire was refined and improved to ensure its content validity. This step is crucial in ensuring that the research instrument effectively captures the information needed to address the research objectives and draw valid conclusions.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure for this study involved several steps. Firstly, the researcher approached each Gulayan sa Paaralan Coordinator in the four elementary schools of Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon to obtain the list of grade 5 learners, who served as the target respondents for the study.

Before administering the questionnaires, a consent form was given to each respondent, ensuring that they were aware of the purpose of the study and that their participation was voluntary. The consent form also emphasized the confidentiality of their responses, assuring them that no personal information would be shared without their consent.

The survey was conducted in the English language, and all participants were asked the same set of questions. The researcher carefully planned and scheduled the survey, taking into consideration the health protocols required during the COVID-19 pandemic. The researcher personally conducted the study, ensuring adherence to the necessary health protocols and safety measures.

After the questionnaires were distributed, the researcher retrieved the completed questionnaires ensure a 100% retrieval rate. The collected data were then tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted to draw meaningful conclusions and address the research objectives.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical treatment for the data analysis in this study involves the use of descriptive statistics, frequency, percentage, mean, t-test, and inferential statistics like analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Descriptive statistics, such as frequency and percentage, were used to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, and area/school. This will provide a clear understanding of the characteristics of the participants in the study.

Frequency- an organized tabulation representation of the number of individuals in each category on the scale of measurement.

Percentage-the use of numbers expressed as a proportion of a whole to present findings and compare results.

The mean was calculated to determine the average level of agricultural skills developed among the grade five learners in the Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon This helped in assessing the overall proficiency of the students in agricultural activities.

Mean – which is also known as the average, is the total sum of values in a sample divided by the number of values in your sample.

Likert Scale

Interpretation of Agricultural Skills Developed Among the Grade 5 Learners

Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	5.44 - 4.45	Highly Skilled
4	4.44 - 3.45	Moderately Skilled
3	3.44 - 2.45	Least Skilled
2	2.44 - 1.45	Fairly Skilled
1	1.44 – 0.00	Not Skilled

Likert Scale - is a rating scale used to measure opinions, attitudes, or behaviors. It consists of a statement or a question, followed by a series of five or seven answer statements

To determine if there is a significant difference in agrarian skills across different profiles (e.g., sex, and area/school), statistical tests such as the t-test and ANOVA were employed. The t-test was used when comparing two groups, such as male and female learners, while ANOVA was used when comparing more than two groups, such as the schools. These tests helped identify if there are significant variations in agricultural skills based on the profiles being examined. By utilizing these statistical treatments, the study was able to analyze the data effectively and draw meaningful conclusions regarding the agricultural skills of the learners in the Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon.

t-test – inferential statistic used to determine if there is a significant difference between the means of two groups and how they are related.

ANOVA - which stands for Analysis of Variance, is a statistical test used to analyze the difference between the means of more than two groups.

Scope and Delimitation

The scope of this study is focused on the development of agricultural skills among students, specifically fifth graders in Plaridel District, Schools Division of Quezon. It does not include an analysis of the perceptions of parents and teachers regarding the implementation of the Gulayan sa Paaralan Program (GPP). The study assesses the learners' basic gardening skills, such as land clearing and preparation, material selection and methods, plant maintenance and care, and another relevant agricultural knowledge.

The research aims to examine any significant differences between the demographic profiles of the learners and the agricultural skills they developed during the implementation of the GPP. The evaluation of their skills was conducted prior to the implementation of the COVID-19 lockdown, which started on March 12, 2020. The study focuses solely on the benefits for fifth-grade children, with the intention of informing

interventions to enhance the program's implementation and further enrich the students' gardening skills.

RESULT

Part 1. Profile of the Respondents

Table 3

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	65	41.7%
Female	91	58.3%
Total	156	100.0%

Table 4

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Area/School

Area / School	Number of Male Learners	Number of Female Learners	Total Number of Learners	Percentage
Concepcion Elementary School	7	10	17	10.90%
Ilosong Elementary School	12	25	37	23.70%
Plaridel Central School	33	45	78	50%
Tanauan Elementary School	13	11	24	15.40%
Total	65	91	156	100%

Part II. Skills Developed Among the Learners due to Gulayan sa Paaralan

Table 5

Essential Skills Developed Among Learners in Terms of Clearing and Land Preparation

Agricultural Skills	Frequency	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Skillfully use the bolo, hoe, and rake in clearing area.	156	3.206	Least Skilled
2. Has the ability to identify different kinds of soil such as loam soil, clay soil and sandy soil.	156	3.149	Least Skilled
3. Can do planning or lay outting of the lot and garden plots using pull push roll measuring scale.	156	3.220	Least Skilled
4. Practice proper spacing of garden plots in a systematic way.	156	3.000	Least Skilled
5. Able to lay out the garden plots with good edges using meter scale, peg, and string.	156	3.173	Least Skilled
6. Marking holes with proper spacing appropriate to the specific gardens veggies.	156	3.341	Least Skilled
7. Level the garden plots using specially made wooden bar.	156	3.241	Least Skilled
8. Enrichment of the soil by adding humus and organic fertilizer into it.	156	3.374	Least Skilled
9. Exercise sterilization of soil and fertilizer mixture especially in nursery to prevent diseases, pests, and fungus brought by decaying materials.	156	3.143	Least Skilled
Total	156	3.206	Least Skilled

Legend:

5 – Highly Skilled 2 – Fairly Skilled
 4 – Moderately Skilled 1 – Not Skilled
 3 – Least Skilled

Table 6

Essential Skills Developed Among Learners in Terms of Selection of Planting Materials and Methods of Planting

Agricultural Skills of Skilled	Frequency	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Selection of seeds and seedlings appropriate to kinds of soil (loam, lay, and sandy soil) as well as to its topography.	156	3.097	Least Skilled
2. Selection of right planting material suitable to weather conditions in the locality.	156	3.203	Least Skilled
3. Garden holes preparation with proper spacing according to each plant classification that requires direct planting.	156	3.210	Least Skilled
4. Indirect planting of selected seeds in the nursery	156	3.087	Least Skilled
Total	156	3.149	Least Skilled

Legend:

5 – Highly Skilled 2 – Fairly Skilled
 4 – Moderately Skilled 1 – Not Skilled
 3 – Least Skilled

Table 7*Essential Skills Developed Among Learners in Terms of Systematic Planting Strategy*

Agricultural Skills	Frequency	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Crop rotation system application	156	3.13	Least Skilled
Companion cropping	156	3.22	Least Skilled
Intercropping	156	3.09	Least Skilled
Total	156	3.147	Least Skilled

Legend:

5 – Highly Skilled 2 – Fairly Skilled
 4 – Moderately Skilled 1 – Not Skilled
 3 – Least Skilled

Table 8*Essential Skills Developed Among Learners in Terms of Maintenance and Caring for Plants*

Agricultural Skills	Frequency	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Removal of weeds and unwanted grass	156	3.08	Least Skilled
Proper cultivation to ensure root nourishment	156	3.01	Least Skilled
Watering the plants by using a pail and sprinkler	156	3.09	Least Skilled
Pest's control	156	3.02	Least Skilled
Proper fertilization and dosing according to plants requirement	156	3.06	Least Skilled
Trellising	156	3.09	Least Skilled
Mulching by using dried leaves or hay	156	3.04	Least Skilled
Proper uses of garden tools	156	3.03	Least Skilled
Total	156	3.053	Least Skilled

Legend:

5 – Highly Skilled 2 – Fairly Skilled
 4 – Moderately Skilled 1 – Not Skilled
 3 – Least Skilled

Table 9*Essential Skills Developed Among Learners in Terms of Identification of Garden Tools and other Materials*

Agricultural Skills	Frequency	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Skillfully identify garden tools such as bolo, shovel, hoe, rake, sharp bar, meter scale as well as sprinkler and pail.	156	3.02	Least Skilled
Able to identify different kinds of organic fertilizer	156	3.05	Least Skilled
Easily identify organic pesticides	156	3.06	Least Skilled
Total	156	3.043	Least Skilled

Legend:

5 – Highly Skilled 3 – Least Skilled 1 – Not Skilled
 4 – Moderately Skilled 2 – Fairly Skilled

Table 10*Essential Skills Developed Among Learners in Terms of Proper Care of Garden Tools*

Agricultural Skills	Frequency	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Provision of stock room for sharp tools like hoe and bolo	156	2.97	Least Skilled
Provision of stock room for fertilizer and pesticides and others of the same kinds	156	2.99	Least Skilled
Proper cleaning of garden tools before bringing it to the stock room	156	2.99	Least Skilled
Total	156	2.983	Least Skilled

Legend:

5 – Highly Skilled 3 – Least Skilled 1 – Not Skilled
 4 – Moderately Skilled 2 – Fairly Skilled

Table 11*Special Skills Developed Among Learners in Terms of Identification and Control of Destructive Insects*

Agricultural Skills	Frequency	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Installation of trap with light against ring borer.	156	2.97	Least Skilled
Smoke application to repel lady bugs.	156	2.88	Least Skilled
Uses of organic pesticides against plant hoppers and aphids	156	2.87	Least Skilled
Total	156	2.874	Least Skilled

Legend:

5 – Highly Skilled 3 – Least Skilled 1 – Not Skilled
 4 – Moderately Skilled 2 – Fairly Skilled

Table 12*Special Skills Developed Among Learners in Terms of Organic Fertilizer Making*

Agricultural Skills	Frequency	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Identification of raw materials such as animal manure, decaying plants, and vegetation as well as kitchen left over and other decaying matters	156	2.98	Least Skilled
Able to demonstrate proper mixing of the raw materials until decomposition have been complete usually after two to three months and be able to use as fertilizer	156	2.94	Least Skilled
Practice proper fermentation procedure of the selected fruits in an anaerobic condition and enhances its decomposition by adding molasses to boost fermentation and eventually resulted to fermented fruit juice and be use as foliar fertilizer.	156	2.96	Least Skilled
Total	156	2.960	Least Skilled

Legend:

5 – Highly Skilled 3 – Least Skilled 1 – Not Skilled
 4 – Moderately Skilled 2 – Fairly Skilled

Table 13*Special Skills Developed Among Learners in Terms of Harvesting and Marketing*

Agricultural Skills	Frequency	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Practice proper harvesting procedure of vegetables of its kind.	156	2.92	Least Skilled
Sorting out of harvested products according to size, weight, and quality.	156	2.98	Least Skilled
Right timing and age of the harvest.	156	2.94	Least Skilled
Ensure proper ventilation and safety of the harvest from destructive insects	156	2.98	Least Skilled
Proper packaging and labeling of the products	156	2.98	Least Skilled
Ability to estimate the prevailing and labeling of the products	156	2.96	Least Skilled
Must know how to sell the products in retail and wholesale.	156	2.96	Least Skilled
Employ good conduct while selling in front of the customer	156	2.94	Least Skilled
Recording and computation of expenses versus capital to determine profit or losses	156	2.90	Least skilled
Total	156	2.968	Least skilled

Legend:

5 – Highly Skilled 3 – Least Skilled 1 – Not Skilled
 4 – Moderately Skilled 2 – Fairly Skilled

Part III. Significant Difference in the Skills of the Learners when Grouped into Profile**Table 14***Significant Difference in the Agricultural Skills of the Learners When Grouped into Profile in Terms of Sex*

Sex	Frequency	Mean
Male	65	3.164
Female	91	2.969

t-value = 1.307 p-value = 0.193 not significant at alpha = .05

Table 15*Significant Difference in Agricultural Skills of the Learners When Grouped into Profile in Terms of Area/Schools*

Area/School	Frequency	Mean
Concepcion Elementary School	17	2.516
Ilosong Elementary School	37	3.117
Plaridel Central School	78	2.855
Tanauan Elementary School	24	3.960
Total	156	3.050

f-value = 13.514 with p-value = .000 significant at alpha = 0.05

Table 16

Significant Difference Between Pairs of Area/Schools Regarding the Development of Agricultural Skills

Duncan^b Area/School	Frequency	Subset for alpha = 0.05		
		1	2	3
Concepcion Elementary School	17	2.516		
Ilosong Elementary School	37		3.117	
Plaridel Central School	78	2.855	2.855	
Tanauan Elementary School	24			3.960
	Sig.	.125	.234	1.000

DISCUSSION

Table 3 shows the distribution of responses according to sex categories. As depicted in the table, there were more female respondents than male respondents. The data reveals that three out of four schools had a higher number of female respondents compared to male respondents, resulting in a total difference of 41.7% males and 58.3% females within the population. Perhaps in the locality of Plaridel there are more females than male, however this data is contrary to the findings on World Gender Ratio by Richie and Roser (2020) wherein the male has numerous birth rate than female. There are about 105 males in every 100 females, but this result varies in every country and localities. According to Hannah Ritchie and Max Roser, the ratio between the number of males and females in a society is referred to as the gender ratio. This ratio is not stable but instead shaped by biological, social, technological, cultural, and economic forces. And in turn the gender ratio itself has an impact on society, demography, and the economy.

In Table 4, the rows representing the percentage within each school indicate the proportion of male and female participants within that school as well as the total population in each school. Plaridel has the highest population of 78 learners followed by Ilosong 17 the Tanauan 24, while Concepcion got the lowest number of the population which is 17 learners.

On the other hand, the percentage within the population column represents the proportion of respondents from each every attending a specific school. According to the table, Plaridel accounted for a population category percentage of 50%. It was followed by Ilosong, which comprised 23.7% of the population, Tanauan with 15.4%, and Concepcion with 10.9%. with a total percentage of 100%. Plaridel Central School has a larger population due to a greater population in the town proper as compared to the schools in different barangays of Ilosong Tanauan and Concepcion where the citizen population is much smaller. This result confirms on the study of Showalter et. al. (2019) where only 15% respondents came from rural areas and 85 % from urban areas. As stated, the Plaridel Central School is in an urban area, so the population is bigger than the three

schools, namely Concepcion Elementary School Ilosong Elementary School and Tanauan Elementary School which are in rural areas.

Table 5 presents different level of agricultural skills in clearing and preparation of land, this also shows that highest agricultural skills acquired by the grade five learners is the organic enrichment of the soil and this is demonstrated by the highest mean of 3.374 while the mean of 3.000 corresponds to the lowest agricultural skills reached by the learners this means that they don't care enough on proper spacing of garden plots because most of their parents are fisherfolk and they don't have enough time nor having the technical knowledge to do it in a systematic way since the municipality is located beside the Lamon Bay area as we have seen in figure No. 2.(location map of Plaridel, Quezon).Lamon Bay is consider as one of the fishing ground of Quezon. According to Bañas et al. (2020) in their study Valuing vanishing coasts: The case of Miagao coastline in Southern Iloilo, Philippines, Coastal communities are dependent to their employment opportunities, resources, goods, and services and the value of the coast. So, as a result, the Plaridel District as located in Lamon bay area so the skill in Agriculture is least skills. Another reason is the environmental influence since fishing is predominant in the area.

Table 6 displays the levels of skill in the selection of planting materials and methods of planting , with this comparison of different skills in this category the learners shows that *garden holes preparation with proper spacing* lead the highest level of skills with a mean value of 3.210 this perhaps in my opinion is because most of the farmers in Plaridel is coconut farmer and they are familiar in digging hole to plant coconut seedling as they have seen from their father. The next skill is followed by selection of right planting materials , selection of seeds and seedlings appropriate to kind of soil ,and lastly the mean value of 3.087 represent the lowest level of skills which is *indirect planting of seeds in the nursery* .Majority of grade 5 learners are not familiar on the nursery operation in the garden because it really needs a technical training on seeds preparation in order to do it the proper way and this confirm the claim of Ibañez Jr. et al. (2022) for lack of training program and seminars in the Gulayan sa Paaralan. As a result, the teachers in EPP in Plaridel District need a quarterly seminar/workshop regarding the different skills in Agriculture.

Table 7 indicates the level of agricultural skills of grade five learners on essentials skills, developed in systematic planting in Gulayan sa Paaralan. Systematic planting is very important in implementing Gulayan sa Paaralan because it is deliberate planting and growing of crops for the purpose of consumption. This could be for food. We noticed that among the inter cropping have the lowest mean value 3.09, followed by crop rotation system application 3.13 then by companion cropping skills 3.22 mean value. This means that the learners have the highest level of skills in companion cropping under its category which is the least skills. All the three values still belong to the least skills, and this is due to insufficient technical training and seminars about proper gardening this confirm claimed of Ibañez Jr. et al. (2022) about Gulayan Sa Paaralan Program

According to case study of Zulfiqar Ali & Shagufta Shahzadi (2023) Teacher training institutions provide prospective teachers with the knowledge, abilities, and as a

result, these institutions are important to ensuring the quality of education. Since education is the foundation of learnings and the pillars of learnings are the teachers, it is tantamount to say that well equipped teachers can provide their students a well-defined knowledge and application of it in whatever endeavor they may have like in agriculture.

Table 8 shows that the level of skills of all respondents the grade five learners fall into the category of least skills and among these the highest mean value went to two skills , the skills of watering the plants using pail and portable sprinkler and the skills of trellising which both fall into the mean of 3.09 while the lowest levels of skills goes to proper cultivation indicating that the learners can cultivate but not in a proper way to protect and nourish the roots. Watering the plants and trellising is most observed by the kids whether in school or in their home, that's why it appears to be the highest mean value. It is said that observation is a part of indirect training. The proper way to protect the roots of plants through cultivating is one of the negligence of the grade 5 learners because some of the grade 5 learners wants to play while actually doing it in the garden they never think that root system of the plant is very critical to the plant nourishing system and this confirm by the study by Jordan et.al., (2020) that kids love to play. There needs to be somewhere to relax and be able to unwind. Working in the garden may seem like playing since they do garden of course outside the room where the surroundings are conducive to playing. This playing attitude of the kids perhaps contributed to the highest skills in trellising skill since this activity resembles like they are playing.

Table 9 shows the level of skills in this table falls into least skills and it is arranged from lowest to highest mean value. This means that identification of organic pesticide is easier than identifying garden tools. This explains that the label in the organic pesticide container truly directs the learners since there is no place label on the garden tools. This proves the findings of Larsen et, al. (2021) that proper labeling of products can make a significant difference. Using organic fertilizer is the best practice in the grade 5 learners in Plaridel District because it is always available in the community. [cow manure, chicken manure, carabao manure, kitchen ways, decaying leaves]. Likewise using organic fertilizer was also recommended for farther innovation by Sanz et, al. (2022). Using organic fertilizer is low cost in Gulayan sa Paaralan and at the same time, it is good for the health for the students and people who eat the vegetables. In addition to this According to Noor et al., (2023) inefficient management of these agro-industrial wastes causes a serious threat to the environment. That's why organic fertilizer production can help to manage those waste besides it is very useful to our plants and vegies.

Table 10 displays the level of skills acquired regarding garden tools proper care with its corresponding mean value and surveyed population. All the learners fall into the least skills level with a very minimal differences of 0.1-0.2 on their mean value as shown in the figure above. Proper care of garden tools are essential to ensure their longevity and effectiveness however the data on the table shows that the proper care of garden tools is not a priority of the grade five learners in Plaridel because they are still young and they do not have enough knowledge and concern to take care of it, besides their parents do not discuss that in the family when at home since majority of the parents concern is all about their job and occupation. One of the sources of income and livelihood

of the local folks around Plaridel, Quezon, is fishing and coconut farming closely related to their environment beside Lamon Bay as presented in Figure No.2 Location Map of the Plaridel. Coconut farming is very different from school gardening since there is no need to cultivate and water the coconut every day, that's why still the learners fall into least skill even though their parents are coco farmer.

Table 11 presents the population, the mean value, and the level of skills under special skills. All the levels of skills belong to the least skills. The mean difference is very minimal with the difference of 0.01 to 0.02 from highest level of skills to lowest level. The Identification and control of destructive insects is not easy for the grade 5 learners because of lack of knowledge. They need to know how to identify destructive insects to control it. According to Singh et. al. (2022) rapid and accurate insect detection is necessary to identify if an insect is neither useful nor destructive to crops. The gulayan coordinator really needs a lot of training from an expert individual to teach them to their students.

It is also needed to identify friendly insects to protect them as they help in the pollination process, giving them a healthy plant.

Table 12 presents the different skills under organic fertilizer making. It also shows the population, the mean, and the level of skills in which all levels fall into least skills. The table shows that the lowest skills is with mean value of 2.94, Able to demonstrate proper mixing of raw materials until decomposition have been complete usually after two or three months and be able to use as fertilizer. While the highest mean fell to 2.98 which is identification of raw materials, The learners got the highest mean on this because the materials are normally available in the locality of Plaridel, and the learners usually seen it in the surroundings. On the other hands proper mixing and decomposition on organic materials takes a lot of time. Even the allotted hours for the subject EPP are only 40 minutes and not enough to perform the activity within a single period. Preparation and mixing of organic fertilizers as well as composting entail a lot of patience so to be more familiarized time is really needed. Jarabese R.G. (2021) confirms that in his study time is needed to master skills in EPP in grade 5.

Table 13 reflects the level of skills of 156 grade five learners wherein everyone falls into least skills. The three skills got the highest mean of 2.98. and they are letter (2,4 and 5) This means that the learners belonging to these categories got the highest understanding among the least skills level. While the lowest understanding belongs to letter (9), this explains that learners have poorest understanding of recording, computation of expenses versus capital. The table shows the Grade 5 learners have a difficulty in recording and computation which explain that many of the respondent have deficiency in Mathematics and that confirms the findings of Kert et. al. (2022). Simple accounting must be learned in gardening since it is like a small business.

Table 14 displays the mean and standard error of mean for the responses from both sexes. The table reveals that male respondents have higher perceived agricultural skills compared to females, with a mean score of 3.164 for males and 2.969 for females.

The standard error of mean values is close to zero, indicating a high level of accuracy in the results.

Barrameda (2022) explained that males may have more knowledge in gardening. They highlighted that gardening is often seen as a physically demanding job that men are more likely to engage in. Furthermore, men are generally more educated about plants and gardening compared to women. Men are most of the time working in the field/farm for hard labor especially in Quezon province unlike in central Luzon where both men and women are working in the farmland. Traditionally, women are associated with nurturing plants and maintaining homes and gardens.

The standard error of mean is 0.1227 for males and 0.0913 for females, indicating that the sample accurately represents the whole population. According to Marek et al. (2022), as the sample size decreases, the standard error of the mean also decreases. In our study, the lower standard error of the mean for males can be attributed to the difference in the number of respondents. It is worth noting that a low standard error suggests that the gathered statistics are accurate.

Karunasingha (2022) discussed that a standard error close to zero indicates that the estimated value precisely represents the actual value. Additionally, it signifies that the sample size effectively represents the entire population of the study.

Table 15 presents the results of the one-way ANOVA test. The table indicates that Tanauan has the highest mean score, suggesting that their learners possess the highest perceived agricultural skills. This outcome can be attributed to the effective leadership efforts of their Gulayan coordinator. Additionally, Tanauan shows the lowest standard deviation, indicating that its findings are the most reliable and accurate compared to the other schools. Concepcion, on the other hand, has the lowest mean score. Despite having a small sample size, it still demonstrates an average standard deviation, which implies that its results are also credible.

Thus, Tanauan Elementary School in rural areas are more participatory rural school. Appraisal as an Approach to Environment Education in urban Community Gardens this is according to S Kordon, PA Miller, CL Bohannon - Land, 2022-mdpi.com.

Table 15 presents the results of Duncan's Multiple Range test, which aims to identify significant differences between pairs of schools regarding the development of agricultural skills. According to the table, the agricultural skills developed by students from Tanauan Elementary School are significantly different from the skills developed by learners in the other three schools.

However, there is no significant difference in agricultural skills between learners in Ilosong Elementary School and Plaridel Central School. Similarly, there is no significant difference between students in Plaridel Elementary School and Concepcion Elementary School.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

The Gulayan sa Paaralan Program (GPP) serves as an effective tool for promoting food security through its feeding program and for acquiring and enhancing students' agricultural skills. It enables individuals to acquire fundamental and specialized agricultural skills that can be applied in their own homes, whether for personal or commercial purposes. However, the study reveals that the overall level of skills among the learners is the least, indicating a need for improvement. Specific areas requiring attention include the identification and proper use of garden tools and addressing issues related to destructive pests. These aspects are crucial for effective garden management, as appropriate tools and pest control measures are necessary for maintaining plant health. Without acquiring the necessary skills for program implementation, the success of gardening and the attainment of program objectives may be compromised.

The study indicates that males demonstrate greater agricultural expertise and talents compared to females. The underlying causes for this difference were not within the scope of this study, suggesting that it could be explored further as a topic for future research.

The results reveal that Tanauan has the highest mean score among the schools in the Plaridel Districts, Schools Division of Quezon, indicating that the Gulayan Coordinator and the School Head have effectively implemented the program in their school.

There is a significant difference between students' sex, and area/school, and their agricultural skills developed during the implementation of the Gulayan sa Paaralan Program. Thus, the null hypothesis must be accepted.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. For stakeholders, particularly the Department of Education (DepEd) and the School Head:
 - 1.1 Implement creative and engaging techniques in agricultural activities. By incorporating fun and interactive elements, students can learn fundamental gardening concepts and methods while enjoying the process, thereby motivating, and encouraging their participation.
 - 1.2 Encourage students to actively engage in gardening by organizing contests or competitions that utilize their horticultural and creative skills. This approach can foster healthy competition and provide an incentive for students to excel in their agricultural pursuits.
 - 1.3 Provide guidance to students throughout the activities, from planting seeds to harvesting crops. Teachers should focus on demonstrating and explaining the

basic principles of gardening and proper procedures, allowing learners to learn firsthand while exploring the gardening process.

1.4 Regularly evaluate learners' skills in various aspects to identify areas that require improvement. This assessment can help tailor instructional approaches and provide targeted support to enhance students' agricultural knowledge and abilities.

1.5 Conduct regular assessments of the performance of GPP coordinators in managing the garden and guiding students. This evaluation will ensure that coordinators are effectively fulfilling their roles and responsibilities, contributing to the overall success of the program.

2. Future researchers working on similar or related topics can use this study as a reference for more in-depth investigations at a more complex level. They can explore factors that influence learners perceived agrarian skills and conduct satisfaction assessments involving various stakeholders.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher declares that compliance with obtaining informed consent was followed, that the respondents were told they had the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

Acknowledgements

The researcher acknowledges with sincerity and profound gratitude the persons with wholehearted cooperation, support, and guidance, especially to all who extended contribution and assistance in various way toward the completion of the study and make this a reality.

Marinduque State College Extension of Graduate Programs to Quezonian Educational College, Incorporated faculty and staff under the leadership of **DR. DIOSDADO P. ZULUETA, SUC** President III.

DR. LEODEGARIO M. JALOS, JR, Designated Chair, Extended Graduate Programs of the Marinduque State College, for sharing his expertise, comments, and approval of this piece of work.

DR. ALEXANDER M. PASCUA, her research adviser for his help, moral support, encouragement, and continuous guidance and advice to make this work possible.

ENGR. EDILBERTO D. ESCOBAR, her brother in-law, and her personal editor during title proposal defense.

MR. WILFREDO Q. VILLAVICENCIO, her personal statistician during title proposal defense.

DR JOY S. MONTEJO, her editor that despite of being busy still have the time to read and edit the manuscript.

To the panelist **DR. WALTER F. GALAROSA**, for his constructive comments and suggestions that greatly contributed to the improvement of this study.

Department of Education Division of Quezon Officials headed by **DR. ELIAS A. ALICAYA, JR.**, the Officer-in-Charge in the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent in Schools Division of Quezon for allowing her to conduct the study.

DR. ORLANDO O. SERDON, DR. CARINA JAMILANO, DR. ANA CLARISSA S. MARIANO, MRS. LOURDES E. GUEVARRA, MRS. MARITES LEGASPI, and MR. RUEL A. CASTILLO, for their time and effort for sharing their knowledge and expertise in the evaluation of the survey questionnaire.

NERRIEL P. BALA, MELBA O. VERDAN, CRISSELLE S. AGUILAR, and CONCEPCION S. BORNALES, Grade 5 advisers in Plaridel District for the cooperation in the distribution of survey questionnaire.

MYRNA O. FRANCISCO, her best friend and co-teacher for help and encouragement to finish the study.

JOELINA P. RODRIGUEZ, her co-member in church for moral support.

ROSEMARIE L. CASTILLO, her inaanak for encouraging her time to time to continue and finish the study.

DR. RIZALIE M. LIM, Dean, QECI Graduate Studies, for valuable time for answering her queries.

MS. LIEZL M. MANOY, for her diligence in receiving every copy from time to time during correction and reediting of the research papers.

MR. ARLLAN B. MUHI, for being so supportive and ready to answer all the researcher's queries.

Above all to our **ALMIGHTY GOD** for His wonderful love and guidance, for the knowledge and wisdom He has given me to make this study a real one.

REFERENCES

- Bañas, J. C., Subade, R. F., Salaum, D. N., & Posa, C. T. (2020). Valuing vanishing coasts: The case of Miagao coastline in southern Iloilo, Philippines. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 184, 105008. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2019.105008>
- Barrameda, T.V., (2017). Surviving in the City Through Home Gardens: A Case Study of Home Gardeners in Barangay UP Campus. https://cswcd.upd.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/PJSD-Vol-9-2017_Barrameda.pdf
- Holmes, E. A., Campbell, M. F., James, W., & Matthews, K. (2020). “Sow, grow, know, and show”: The impact of school gardens on student self-perception in the Mississippi delta. *Ecology of Food and Nutrition*, 60(2), 140-162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03670244.2020.1807343>
- Ibañez Jr., R. Y., Velza, J. F., Castillo, I., & Bartolay, R. (2022). Status of Gulayan Sa Paaralan (School Garden) Program in Public Elementary and Secondary Schools of Cawayan, Masbate, Philippines: Basis for Extension Activities. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 3(12), 2574–2588. <http://dx.doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.03.12.11>
- Jarabese, R. G. (2021). UTILIZATION OF COMPETENCY-BASED - MULTIMEDIA-ASSISTED INTERACTIVE LEARNING LESSON EXPERIENCE (MILE) TO ENHANCE THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE FIVE PUPILS IN EDUKASYONG PANTAHANAN AT PANGKABUHAYAN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/download/60/59/59>
- Jarabese, R. G. (2021). UTILIZATION OF COMPETENCY-BASED-MULTIMEDIA-ASSISTED INTERACTIVE LEARNING LESSON EXPERIENCE (MILE) TO ENHANCE THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE FIVE PUPILS IN EDUKASYONG PANTAHANAN AT PANGKABUHAYAN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(05), 376-381. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/JG4SV>
- Jordan, A., & Rees, E. (2020). Children’s views on well-being and what makes a happy life, UK: 2020. United Kingdom: National Office of Statistics. https://data.london.gov.uk/download/ep56w/qn8/Children%20s%20views%20on%20well-being%20and%20what%20makes%20a%20happy%20life%2C%20UK_%202020.pdf
- Karunasingha, D. S. K. (2022). Root mean square error or mean absolute error? Use their ratio as well. *Information Sciences*, 585, 609-629. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2021.11.036>
- Kert, S. B., Yeni, S., & Fatih Erkoç, M. (2022). Enhancing computational thinking skills of students with disabilities. *Instructional Science*, 50(4), 625-651. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-022-09585-6>
- Larsen, A. E., Claire Powers, L., & McComb, S. (2021). Identifying and characterizing pesticide use on 9,000 fields of organic agriculture. *Nature Communications*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25502-w>

- Maeder, P., Fliessbach, A., Dubois, D., Gunst, L., Fried, P., & Niggli, U. (2002). Soil fertility and biodiversity in organic farming. *Science*, 296(5573), 1694-1697. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1071148>
- Marek, S., Tervo, B., Clemmens, C., Calabro, F. J., & Montez, D. F. (2022). Reproducible brain-wide association studies require thousands of individuals. *Nature*.
- Mariappan, K., Karthikeyan, & Zhou, D. (2019). A Threat of Farmers' Suicide and the Opportunity in Organic Farming for Sustainable Agricultural Development in India. *Sustainability*, 11(8), 2400. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11082400>
- Mourão, I., Moreira, M. C., Almeida, T. C., & Brito, L. M. (2019). Perceived changes in well-being and happiness with gardening in urban organic allotments in Portugal. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology*, 26(1), 79–89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504509.2018.1469550>
- Noor, R. S., Sun, Y., Aslam, W., & Umair, M. (2023). Sustainable production and characterization of integrated composting systems of organic biomass and inorganic amendments. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-023-03883-w>
- Piñol, M.F.(2020). Sec. Manny F. Piñol meets with Bicol farmers and turns over agri assistance. *Umasenso*, 26(1). Retrieved from <https://bicol.da.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/UMAsenso1stQ2017.pdf>
- Pollin, S., & Retzlaff-Fürst, C. (2021). The school garden: A social and emotional place. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.567720>
- Ritchie, H., Roser, M., & Rosado, P. (2020). CO₂ and greenhouse gas emissions. Our world in data. <https://ourworldindata.org/gender-ratio>
- Sanz, C., Casado, M., Navarro-Martin, L., Cañameras, N., Carazo, N., Matamoros, V., Bayona, J. M., & Piña, B. (2022). Implications of the use of organic fertilizers for antibiotic resistance gene distribution in agricultural soils and fresh food products. A plot-scale study. *Science of The Total Environment*, 815, 151973. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.151973>
- Sayadi, S., Tsatsaronis, G., Morosuk, T., Baranski, M., Sangi, R., & Müller, D. (2019). Exergy-based control strategies for the efficient operation of building energy systems. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 241, 118277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118277>
- Shah, A. N., Tanveer, M., Abbas, A., Yildirim, M., Shah, A. A., Ahmad, M. I., Wang, Z., Sun, W., & Song, Y. (2021). Combating dual challenges in maize under high planting density: Stem lodging and kernel abortion. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2021.699085>
- Showalter, D., Hartman, S. L., Johnson, J., & Klein, B. (2019). Why Rural Matters 2018-2019: The Time Is Now. A Report of the Rural School and Community Trust. Rural School and Community Trust. <https://doi.org/10.35608/ruraled.v40i3.930>
- Singh, K. U., Kumar, A., Raja, L., Kumar, V., Singh kushwaha, A. K., Vashney, N., & Chhetri, M. (2022). An artificial neural network-based pest identification and control in smart agriculture using wireless sensor networks. *Journal of Food Quality*, 2022, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/5801206>
- Taghikhah, F., Voinov, A., Shukla, N., & Filatova, T. (2021). Shifts in consumer behavior towards organic products: Theory-driven data analytics. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 61, 102516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2021.102516>

- Tira, M. (2020). About the sustainability of urban settlements. *TeMA-Journal of Land Use, Mobility and Environment*, 361-371. <https://doi.org/10.6092/1970-9870/6984>
- Yadav, P. S., Kewat, M., Jha, A., Hemalatha, K. S. V., & Verma, B. (2023). Effect of sowing management and herbicides on the weed dynamics of berseem (*Trifolium alexandrinum*). Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7742060>
- Yadav, S. P., Lahutiya, V., Ghimire, N. P., Yadav, B., & Paudel, P. (2023). Exploring innovation for sustainable agriculture: A systematic case study of permaculture in Nepal. *Heliyon*, 9(5), e15899. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e15899>
- Zulfiqar Ali, & Shagufta Shahzadi. (2023). A case study of the administrative practices in public teacher trainings institutions affiliated with the University of Karachi (Pakistan). *International Journal of Social Science & Entrepreneurship*, 3(3), 373-388. <https://doi.org/10.58661/ijssse.v3i3.209>